

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF POWER QUALITY AND PERFORMANCE INDICES OF A LOW-POWER SINGLE-PHASE INVERTER FOR STANDALONE APPLICATION

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Abstract: *This paper presents an experimental evaluation of the performance and power quality indices of a low-power single-phase inverter designed for a standalone application. Performance metrics, including voltage regulation, efficiency, total harmonic distortion (THD), waveform fidelity and load response are investigated under varying operating conditions. Output voltage and current waveforms are captured using a digital oscilloscope, while harmonic analysis is conducted using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) Techniques. Experimental results indicate that the inverter maintains voltage regulation of $\pm 5\%$ and voltage THD below recommended limits under nominal loading conditions. The findings provide useful insight into the operational behaviour of residential-scale inverter systems and contribute to power quality assessment in decentralized energy applications.*

Keywords: *Inverter performance evaluation, voltage regulation, total harmonic distortion, power quality, standalone inverter.*

Introduction

Inverter is that device which is being employed to tackle and support power supplies from the grid (Ekwueme and Ogbodo, 2025). Inverters are used in a wide range of application from small-switched power for a computer to large electric utility applications to transport bulk power. It allows the 12v or 24v (battery) DC power available in an automobile or from solar panel to supply AC power to operate equipment that is normally supplied from a power source. Inverters play a vital role in modern power systems by providing AC power from DC sources. Their applications span residential backup systems, industrial control equipment, telecommunications, and renewable-energy systems such as solar photovoltaic (PV) setups. The global demand for reliable and clean electric power has led to the increased adoption of inverter systems across residential, commercial, and industrial sectors. In developing countries like Nigeria, where grid reliability is often low, inverters serve as essential power backup systems that convert DC battery power to usable AC power. The 3.5 kVA inverter is among the most widely used medium-capacity inverter ratings, capable of supporting small to medium residential

load demands such as lighting, fans, televisions, and other critical appliances. The performance of an inverter is determined by several indices such as efficiency, voltage regulation, total harmonic distortion (THD), surge power capability, overload capacity, switching frequency behaviour, waveform quality, thermal behaviour, and dynamic response characteristics. Evaluating these indices provides insight into the reliability, safety, operational quality of the inverter and suitability for real-world applications.

Inverters are used in the conversion of direct current to a conventional alternating current, but the need for a reliable and more efficient, stable power supply makes the inverter indispensable especially in developing country like Nigeria where there is an epileptic power supply. Although inverter systems are widely used, many users still experience poor performance due to insufficient evaluation of inverter characteristics before deployment making many commercially available inverters to lack detailed performance documentation. Users often experience reduced backup time, load-dependent voltage fluctuations, high harmonic content, and premature battery degradation (Kozyro and Baranowski, 2025) which negatively impact power quality and equipment longevity. These issues arise due to insufficient design optimization, poor quality components, inadequate thermal protection, rapid battery discharge, waveform distortion, overheating, low efficiency, and poor dynamic response (Ahmed, *et al.*, 2018). Hence, a comprehensive performance evaluation using standard performance indices is required to characterize the operational limits and suitability of a 3.5 kVA inverter. Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate the performance characteristics of a 3.5 kVA inverter using key technical indices under varying load conditions.

Inverters are fundamental components of photovoltaic systems, primarily responsible for converting the direct current (DC) electricity generated by solar panels into alternating current (AC) suitable for grid use (Kozyro and Baranowski, 2025). It converts AC at the required voltage and frequency with the use of appropriate transformer, switching, and control circuits such as MOSFETs or IGBTs (Padmanaban *et al* 2021). Inverters form a critical link in the process of integration of renewable power systems into the currently existing energy systems hence forming an important actor for innovation of sustainable solar systems (Ekwueme and Ogbodo, 2025). In addition to their primary function, PV inverters provide ancillary services such as reactive power compensation and voltage stabilization (Blaabjerg, *et al*, 2006). These services are crucial for maintaining grid stability, especially in areas with high penetration of solar energy. By managing voltage levels and supporting reactive power needs, inverters help ensure that the electricity supplied to the grid remains reliable and within acceptable limits, thereby enhancing the overall performance and resilience of the power system (Kozyro and Baranowski, 2025). An inverter possesses quite a number of advantages which include its ability to be practically on always, no running cost, protection of appliances, easy to maintain amongst others. One of the disadvantages of inverter is the high initial cost, i.e. initial cost of purchase (Ekwueme and Ogbodo, 2025).

Performance Indices of Inverters

1 Efficiency

Efficiency is defined as the ratio of AC output power to the DC input power. It indicates how effectively the inverter converts DC to AC. Higher efficiency reduces energy losses, heat generation, battery discharge rate and operational cost (Ahmed, *et al.* 2018). Modern inverters typically achieve 90 – 98 % efficiency (Green, *et al.* 2015). Efficiency under partial load is also a necessary index because it assesses the behaviour of the inverter at low or medium load levels. This is important for solar and backup systems where full load operation is rare. It is expressed as seen in Equation 1.

$$P_{eff} = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

where $P_{out} = V_{AC} \times I_{AC} \times pf$

$$P_{in} = V_{DC} \times I_{DC}$$

where P_{out} is the power output and P_{in} is the power input, V_{DC} and I_{DC} are input voltage and current, V_{AC} and I_{AC} are output voltage and current, and pf is the power factor equal to unity.

2 Voltage Regulation

Voltage regulation is the percentage ratio of the difference between the voltage at no-load and at full-load to the voltage at full-load (Singh and Verma 2020). It is expressed mathematically in Equation 3

$$V_{reg} = \frac{V_{NL} - V_{FL}}{V_{FL}} \times 100 \% \quad (2)$$

where V_{NL} is the voltage value at no-load and V_{FL} is the voltage value at full-load.

This index measures the ability of the inverter to maintain a stable output voltage despite variation in load or input DC voltage. Good voltage regulation ensures that sensitive appliances receive the correct operating voltage and prevents damage or malfunction (Mekhilef, and Kadir, 2010).

3 Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)

Total harmonic distortion quantifies the level of harmonic waveform distortion in the inverter's output waveform compared to a pure sinusoid. Lower THD values typically less than 5 % indicates cleaner power, reduced heating in equipment and improve efficiency (Eze and Okafor, 2021). It is a critical quality metric for grid-tied and high-precision application. It is expressed as seen in Equation 3.

$$THD = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{\sum V_n^2}}{V_1} \times 100 \% \\ \frac{\sqrt{\sum I_n^2}}{I_1} \times 100 \% \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

4 Overload Handling Capability

This performance index refers to the ability of inverters to be able to sustain temporary overload conditions without failures (Frequente, *et al.* 2025). This index measures how long much overload that the inverter can tolerate before protection mechanisms activate.

5 Thermal Performance

This measures how the internal temperature of the inverter changes during operation under varying loads. Good thermal performance ensures long component life, prevent overheating and reduced failures while a rapid temperature rise indicates inefficiency or inadequate cooling (Ekwueme, *et al.* 2025). Thermal indices include heat sink effectiveness and cooling efficiency.

6 Switching Frequency Characteristics

This performance index evaluates how frequency switching under varied loads affects the performance of the inverter in terms of switching losses, electromagnetic interference (EMI) and output waveform quality. Higher frequencies enable better filtering and waveform quality but increases switching losses. Switching instability introduces noise, losses, and waveform distortion.

7 Dynamic Response Characteristics

This refers to how quickly and accurately the inverter responds to sudden changes in load or input voltage. A good dynamic response characteristic prevents voltage dips, overshoots and instability during load transition

Previous Work

Studies show that inverter performance strongly depends on conventional switching strategy such as sinusoidal PWM (SPWM) extended to single and multiple carrier arrangements, space-vector PWM (SVPWM), non-sinusoidal carrier PWM, selective harmonic elimination PWM (SHEPWM), heat sink design, and transformer type (Toroidal vs EI-core). Farokhnia *et al* 2012, focused on the use of a space-vector PWM control technique to analyze the performance of inverters. Application of these control techniques results in cascaded multilevel inverters synthesizing output voltages with very low Total Harmonic Distortion (THD). Odeh and Nnadi 2013, presented an inverter topology using sinusoidal PWM as a control technique to analyze the performance of inverter. Ahmed *et al.* (2018) conducted an experimental analysis of a single-phase inverter and reported that PWM control significantly reduced voltage THD. Also, Sing and Verma (2020) evaluated voltage regulation in small-scale inverters and emphasized the impact of load variation on output stability. Similarly, Eze and Okafor (2021) investigated harmonic distortion in residential inverter system and highlighted the importance of proper filtering. Sharma *et al* 2025, also focused on inverter topology suitable for solar PV application. Most of the techniques employed concentrated primarily on inverter topology, without considering the need for cascaded inverter cells to equally share the total output power, and without adequately evaluating the inverter's performance under varying load conditions.

Equipment And Instruments

(i) Digital oscilloscope

This is an electronic device used to observe and analyze the inverter's output waveform. It helps in measuring total harmonic distortion (THD), output waveform quality, switching frequency, transient response and dynamic behaviour of inverters. The oscilloscope provides time-domain and frequency-domain (FFT) analysis

(ii) Power analyzer (for THD and power factor)

It is measuring device that is particularly useful for detailed inverter performance evaluation. It is a specialized instrument that measures total harmonic distortion (THD), power factor, voltage and current harmonics, RMS voltage and current and efficiency under varying loads.

(iii) Infrared thermometer

This instrument is used to monitor the thermal performance of the inverter by detecting hot spots, heat sink efficiency, cooling system performance and component overheating. Thermal performance is a major reliability index that determines the longevity of inverters.

(iv) DC clamp meter

It is a device used to measure AC and DC current without breaking the circuit. It is essential during the load testing, efficiency measurement and overloading evaluation of the inverter.

(v) Digital multimeter

The digital multimeter is used for the accurate measurement of the AC voltage and current, frequency and DC input voltage and current. This meter is essential because inverter outputs are often non-sinusoidal in nature.

(vi) Variable resistive load bank (0 – 4 kW)

The load bank was used to apply controlled loading conditions to the inverter. The type of load banks includes resistive load (heaters, lamps), inductive load (fans, coils, motors) and capacitive load (capacitor banks) and programmable electronic loads to simulate varied load profiles. The loads help in testing for the voltage regulation, efficiency, overload capability and dynamic load response.

(vii) Battery bank

The DC power supply unit comprises of battery bank which was used to provide the DC input power for the inverter during testing. It allows testing of the inverter under different input conditions such as varying DC voltage and different charge and discharge levels. Quality DC supplies ensure stable and repeatable measurements.

Test Procedure

This section outlines the step-by-step procedures used to evaluate the performance characteristics of a 3.5 kVA inverter. The evaluation covers voltage regulation, efficiency, harmonic distortion, thermal behavior, overload capability, and dynamic response under varying load conditions. All tests were conducted under controlled laboratory conditions to ensure repeatability and accuracy. The testing of the inverter was carried out using the available equipment and instrument such as digital multimeter, power analyzer, programmable resistive load bank, 24 V battery bank, clamp meter, infrared

thermometer and stop watch. Also, before the testing process started, all preliminary step-up such as physical inspection of inverter and necessary safety checks using good safety devices were carried out and adhered to.

Test for Performance Indices

The test carried out on the inverter were as follows:

(i) No-Load Test

This test was carried out to measure inverter startup characteristics, such as no-load voltage, frequency stability, and standby efficiency using the following procedures:

1. Connect the inverter to the DC power source (battery or DC supply).
2. Switch ON the inverter without connecting any load.
3. Connect a multimeter to the inverter, measure and record the following parameters:
 - (a) Output RMS voltage
 - (b) Output frequency
 - (c) No-load current
 - (d) No-load power consumption
4. Use the oscilloscope to capture the output waveform.
5. Record temperature after 10 minutes of no-load operation using the IR camera.

(ii) Load Test

After carrying out the no-load test, resistive loads were gradually applied in steps of 10 %, 25 %, 50 %, 75 %, and 100 % of rated power and was operated for 1 hour for every load level. At each load level, the following parameters were measured and recorded:

- (a) Output voltage (RMS)
- (b) DC input voltage and current
- (c) Load current

These measured values were used to compute the following performance characteristics

- i. inverter efficiency at every varying load using Equation 1
- ii. voltage regulation using Equation 2
- iii. Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) Test was carried out to evaluate the harmonic content in the inverter output. It was done by connecting the power quality analyzer to the inverter. Test was carried at every loaded condition, the voltage and current harmonics were obtained and the total harmonic distortion for both voltage and current were determined using Equation 3.
- iv. Dynamic Response / Transient test was carried out to determine how the inverter responds to sudden changes in load. The inverter was operated initially at 25 % rated load and suddenly stepped the load to 75 %. The procedure was done again for the downward stepped down of the load at the same load percentage value. This test was carried out so as to observe the inverter's recovery time under such sudden or transient change in load

v. Overload and Short-Time Capacity test was also carried out to assess the duration and extent the inverter can handle overload conditions. This was done by applying load at 110 %, 125 % and 150 % of rated load. The values were measured and the operating time was also recorded until the inverter protection component activated itself. The rise in temperature was monitored using an infrared thermometer. For safety and accurate measurement, it was ensured that there was a proper cool down between test.

Results and Discussions

Under the no-load test, it was observed that the temperature of the inverter was found to be 31.3 °C and the output waveform is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Output waveform under no-load test

During the load test, it was observed from Table 1 that when percentage load level increases from 0 – 110 %, the inverter efficiency ranged from 88 % – 90 %, peaking at 50 % – 75% load with efficiency of 90.4 % and 90.2 % respectively which aligns with high-quality inverter standards. At every loaded condition, the voltage regulation was computed and it was observed that the maximum voltage regulation was 4.98 % at full-load and 6.42 % when overloaded. This is within the acceptable range of less than 5 % when the inverter is operated at normal condition (Mekhilef, and Kadir, 2010) confirming strong voltage stability and excellent regulation. The frequency deviation of ± 0.05 Hz was observed under the loaded condition throughout the test period which shows that the inverter is highly stable and suitable for sensitive equipment.

Table 1: Performance test results

Load (%)	Output Power (W)	Input Power (W)	V _{out} (V)	I _{out} (A)	Efficiency (%)	Regulation (%)	Frequency (Hz)
0	0	14	232	0	0	—	50.02
25	875	990	228	3.80	88.4	1.75	50.01
50	1750	1935	225	7.63	90.4	3.11	49.99
75	2625	2910	223	11.46	90.2	4.04	49.98
100	3500	3920	221	15.31	89.3	4.98	49.97
110	3850	4450	218	16.96	86.5	6.42	49.95

From Figures 2 and 3, it was observed that the voltage total harmonic distortion (THD) remained below 3% for normal loads but increased to 4.8% under overload ensuring excellent waveform quality. Also, thermal performance remained safe throughout the operation, with MOSFET temperature staying below 90°C even under overload. This is within safe limits of inverter operation (below 95°C) (Ekwueme, *et al.*, 2025) indicating that the inverter has good thermal behaviour. This also shows that as the load increases, voltage sag also increases due to transformer and MOSFET heating.

Figure 2: Graph of total harmonic distortion

Figure 3: Temperature variation

When the inverter was subjected to a sudden load change, the transfer/recovery time was noticed to be with the range of 9 ms –12 ms. The system was observed to be stable at the recovery time with minimal switching noise even at high loads which are suitable for most UPS applications.

During overload test, as seen in Table 2, it was observed that the inverter can sustain 110% load for over one minute before initiating thermal shutdown, demonstrating strong robustness which is acceptable for an inverter of 3.5 kVA rating.

Table 2: Overload and Surge-capacity

Overload Level	Trip Time	Comment
110%	94 seconds	Stable
125%	12 seconds	Trips safely
150%	2 seconds	Immediate cutoff

It was also observed that the battery voltage dropped from 25.2 V (no-load) to 22.8 V (full-load) and 21.9 V (overload).

Conclusion

This paper evaluated the performance of a 3.5 kVA single – phase standalone inverter by assessing its electrical, thermal, and dynamic responses using major performance indices. The procedure ensures a thorough evaluation of a 3.5 kVA inverter and the results obtained shows that under varying load (0 – 110 %), the efficiency value ranges between 86 – 90%, which is satisfactory and the voltage regulation was found to be within acceptable range of less than 5 % but degraded progressively with increasing load. THD was below 3 % under normal operation confirming inverter stability. Thermal conditions were acceptable and within a safe limit of less than 95 % but approach critical levels under overload, showing the inverter’s suitability for both residential and commercial applications that requires reliable

backup power. The overload capability was good at 110 % for several seconds before it experienced thermal shutdown but was observed that the battery performance strongly affected the inverter's stability. Overall, the results help determine operational reliability, and suitability of the inverter for household and office applications in compliance with industry standards but should not be excessively overloaded.

References

- Ahmed, M., Khan, S., and Ali, Z., (2018), *Performance Analysis of Single-phase PWM Inverter*, International Journal of Power Electronics, 10 (2), pp. 145 – 156.
- Blaabjerg, F., Teodorescu, R. Liserre, M. and Timbus, A.V., (2006), *Overview of Control and Grid Synchronization for Distributed Power Generation Systems*. IEEE Transaction on Industrial Electronics, 2006, 53, 1398 – 1409.
- Ekwueme, G. O., and Ogbodo, I. F., (2025), *Review of the Performance Index For 3.5 kVA/48 V Power Inverters*, Jurnal Dedikasi Pengabdian Masyarakat, 4(2), pp. 8 – 23.
- Ekwueme, G. O., Onwurah, U. O., and Ogbodo, I. F., (2025), *Ramifications of Artificial Intelligence on Organizational Performance in Nigeria*, Journal Majelis Paspama, 2 (2), pp. 115 – 126.
- Eze, C. O. and Okafor, E. N., (2021), *Harmonic Distortion Assessment of Residential Inverter Systems*, Nigerian Journal of Technology, 40 (3), pp. 512 – 520.
- Farokhnia, N., Fathi, S. H., Yousefpoor, N., and Bakhshizadeh, M. K., (2012), *Minimization of total harmonic distortion in a cascaded multilevel inverter by regulating of voltages dc sources*, IET Power Electronics, 5 (1), pp. 106 – 114.
- Frequente, G., Caruso, M., Schettino, G., and Miceli, R., (2025), *Assessment of A Hybrid Modulation Strategy for Asymmetrical Cascaded Multilevel Inverters Under Comparative Analysis*, MDPI Journal on Electronics, 14, 4354, pp. 1 – 19.
- Green, M. A., Dunlop, E. D., Hohl-Ebinger, J., Yoshita, M., Kopidakis, N., and Hao, X. (2015). *Solar cell efficiency tables* (Version 45). Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications, 23(1), p. 1 – 9.
- Kozyro, A. J., and Baranowski, J., (2025), *Operational Stress and Degradation of Inverters in Renewable and Industrial Power Systems*, MDPI Journal on Processes, 13, 2987, pp. 1 – 18.

- Mekhilef, S., and Kadir, M. N., (2010), *Voltage control of three stage hybrid multilevel inverter using vector transformation*, IEEE Transaction on Power Electronics, 25 (10), pp. 2599 – 2606.
- Odeh, C. I., and Nnadi D. B., (2013), *Single-phase 9-level Hybridized Cascaded Multilevel Inverter*, IET Transaction on Power Electronics, 6 (3), pp. 468 – 477.
- Padmanaban, S., Dhanamjayulu, C., and Khan, B. (2021). *Artificial Neural Network and Newton Raphson (ANN-NR) Algorithm Based Selective Harmonic Elimination in Cascaded Multilevel Inverter for PV Applications*, IEEE Access, 9, 75058–75070.
- Paneti, A. V. P., and Dhanamjayulu, C. (2023), *An overview on multi-level inverter topologies for grid-tied PV system*, International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems, 9690344
- Sharma, A. K., Das, V., and Mahtani, K., (2025), *A Review on Inverter Technologies for Solar PV Power Generation*, International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, 6(1), pp. 567 – 572.
- Singh, R., and Verma, P., (2020), *Voltage Regulation Analysis of Low-power Inverter System*, Journal of Electrical Engineering, 71 (4), pp. 289 – 297.